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The relationship between Knowledge Management with Organizational Effectiveness in the Youth and Sports Ministry's staff

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between knowledge management and organizational effectiveness in the Youth and Sports Ministry's staff. The study population consisted of all employees of the Ministry of Youth and Sports (N= 430) which among them, 203 people, according to Morgan table and were randomly selected. Hsu (2002) organizational effectiveness questionnaire and Probst et al (2000) knowledge management questionnaire were used to collect data. Also, Shapiro Wilk, correlation and multiple regression analysis tests were used for data analysis. The results showed a significant relationship between knowledge management and organizational effectiveness ($p \leq 0/05$). In addition, knowledge management was able to predict organizational effectiveness. Also, dimensions of knowledge management were able to account organizational effectiveness for 35% of the variance. As well as, application of knowledge and recording knowledge had the highest significant potential predictable for organizational effectiveness. Considering the results, pay attention to manage of knowledge management of workers can be considered as one factor affecting the promotion of organizational effectiveness in all organizations managers, including sports organizations.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Knowledge, Sport

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